

Selectivity Coefficients of Trace Elements on a Montmorillonite Clay and a Humic Acid System

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Selectivity coefficients of a number of ion pairs for a montmorillonite clay and a humic acid system have been calculated from the ion-exchange data obtained with trace element cations Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , and Cr^{3+} and H^+ , Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , and Al^{3+} respectively. These have been plotted against the equilibrium concentration of the added cation. The graphs show, except in a few cases only, a wide variation of selectivity coefficient. The deviations are generally more marked in the low concentration range, but at the higher range of concentration, the trend is towards approximately constant values.

The results point out definitely the polyfunctional nature of the clay surface and humic acid. An approximate idea regarding the relative behaviour of ions on the clay systems, humic acid, and humates investigated has been obtained from a comparison of the selectivity parameters calculated at equilibrium concentrations equal to the saturation capacities of the ion exchangers.

The reversible character of ion-exchange reactions has led many to apply the law of mass action to express quantitatively the distribution of ions between the two phases, namely, solid-exchanger phase and the solution phase. In absence of complicating effects, such as those due to formation of complexes in solution, the distribution of exchanging ions between the ion exchanger and the solution is determined by their concentrations in the exchanger and in the solution and by their relative affinities for the exchanger. The affinity of a single ion for an exchange group in an ion exchanger cannot be determined, but the relative affinity for the exchanger of two ions, which are competing for the same exchange site, can be. As the reactions are reversible and stoichiometric, these can be represented by the following equations :

Exchange between ions of the same valency:

The equilibrium constants of the above equations can be written as:

$$K^B_A = \frac{(B_R^{\nu^+}) (A_S^{\nu^+})}{(A_R^{\nu^+}) (B_S^{\nu^+})} \quad \dots \quad (1a)$$

$$K^C_D = \frac{(C_R^{2+}) (D_S^+)^2}{(D_R^+)^2 (C_S^{2+})} \quad \dots \quad (2a)$$

$$K^M_D = \frac{(M_R^{3+}) (D_S^+)^3}{(D_R^+)^3 (M_S^{3+})} \quad \dots \quad (3a)$$

$$K^M_C = \frac{(M_R^{3+})^2 (C_S^{2+})^3}{(C_R^{2+})^3 (M_S^{3+})^2} \quad \dots \quad (4a)$$

where the expressions in parenthesis denote concentration and subscripts R and S denote the exchanger and the solution phase respectively. Since active masses have been assumed

to be equal to the concentrations, the K expressions may be called "concentration equilibrium quotients" or "selectivity coefficients". The point of interest is whether, in practice, such expressions are constants. Marshall and Garcia¹ have proposed "selectivity number" to avoid any false impression of constancy. The relative affinity of the two ions for an ion exchanger is determined by the magnitude of the selectivity coefficient. Considering equation (1a), for instance, if K_A^B is greater than unity and there are no complicating effects in solution, then the exchanger phase has a greater affinity for ion B than ion A. If it is less than unity, the affinity for ion A is greater than that for ion B. If it is equal to unity, then both the ions have got the same affinity for the exchanger.

It follows from the above equations that, if the ratio of the concentrations raised to appropriate powers of the two ions in the exchanger is plotted against the corresponding ratio of their concentrations in solution, a straight line should be obtained with a gradient which is equal to the selectivity coefficient. This conclusion is valid when (i) the ion-exchange sites are of the same bonding energy and (ii) the external solution is dilute. In fact, many authors, such as Kressman and Kitchener², have found K values to be approximately constant for a given exchange reaction.

Furthermore, as the K_A^B function is dimensionless, it is not comparable with K_D^C , K_D^M , or K_C^M values, if these are expressed as molarities for the solution and mole or equivalent fractions for the exchanger. Consequently, it is impossible to state whether a bivalent ion has a greater affinity than a univalent ion for the same exchanger. Nevertheless, it is found that if the external solution is dilute, ions of higher valency are more strongly bound than those of lower valency³.

Accurate experiments by Duncan and Lister⁴ have shown that K values are not true constants. These vary appreciably with the ionic composition of the aqueous phase (e.g., the nature of the non-exchanging ion, particularly with multivalent ion salts) and with the ionic composition of the exchanger phase.

It is now clear that allowance must be made both for activity-coefficient effects and for swelling-energy effects in any comprehensive theory of selectivity. The major difficulty lies in estimating the activity-coefficient effects in the exchanger phase.

EXPERIMENTAL

The hydrogen clay was prepared by electrolysing the clay fraction ($<2\mu$) isolated from a sample of Akli bentonite. It contains montmorillonite as the only clay mineral. The b.e.c. of one sample (A), as determined by the KCl-KOH method of Ganguly⁵, is equal to 78.0 m.e./100 g. A finer fraction (A₁) of the same clay has a b.e.c. of 83.0 m.e./100 g. These two fractions were used for the exchange study against the trace element cations. The pH of a 4.51% colloidal suspension, which was used in this investigation, was 4.0.

1. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, **63**, 1603.

2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 1190, 1201, 1209.

3. Calmon and Kressman, "Ion Exchangers in Organic and Biochemistry", Interscience Publishers, Inc., New York, N.Y., 1957, Chapter 2, p. 58.

4. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 3285.

5. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1951, **55**, 1417.

Cu-, Mn-, and Zn-clays were prepared by treating in a centrifuge the H-clay (A) with 0.25 *M* solutions (*pH* 4.0) of CuSO_4 , MnSO_4 , and $\text{Zn}(\text{OAc})_2$, respectively, in 7 to 8 instalments (i.e., nearly a litre of solution for 100 ml H-clay). The leached clays were washed free of electrolytes, also in the centrifuge, with as small an amount of acidulated water (*pH* 4) as possible. Three to four instalments of 200 ml, each, were required for clay salts prepared from 200 ml of H-clay. This precaution was taken to prevent hydrolysis of the clay salts. These were then suspended in double distilled water.

Ni-, Co-, and Cr-clays were prepared from the fine clay fraction (A_1) by exactly similar methods as described above. For the preparation of Cr-clay, $\text{Cr}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3$ solution of *pH* 1.9 was used.

To a known sample of the clay-salt suspension was added an equal quantity of *N/15*- H_2SO_4 , kept at 60° to 70° for about 1½ hour, and the clay was then leached with *N/30*- H_2SO_4 (total volume of leachate was 200 ml in five or six instalments for 20 ml clay salt) and the content of the particular cation in the leachate was determined. Not all the adsorbed metal ion could be exchanged in this way.

Humic acid was extracted from Padegaon B soil (black cotton soil from Bombay) by treating 100 g. of the soil with 2 litres of 0.25 *M*- Na_2CO_3 solution. After 48 hours of reaction and settling, the supernatant dark liquid containing Na-humate was siphoned off. It was then coagulated by a little excess of HCl and finally purified by electro dialysis. Mn-, Cu-, and Ni-humates were prepared by methods used for the preparation of the respective clay salts.

Exchange Study

The mixtures of the clay and the salt solution, added at concentrations varying between 0.5 and 4.0 times the symmetry concentration, were made to a definite volume (usually 40 ml), shaken manually, and kept overnight, or, for a rapid equilibrium, shaken in a mechanical shaker for 2 to 3 hours at room temperature. The mixtures were then centrifuged and the clear solutions were analysed.

The H-clay (A_1) was used for exchange study against the cations Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Cr^{3+} , whereas Mn^{2+} was exchanged against H-clay (A).

In exchange study against H-clay with trace element cations, sulphate solutions of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cr^{3+} , Zn^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} were used. Sulphate solutions of Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , and Mg^{2+} were employed when these cations were exchanged against Ni-, Co-, Cr-, Zn-, and Mn-clays. With Cu-clay, the chlorides of Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , and Ba^{2+} were used. Cu was determined iodimetrically with this sulphate; Mn, either by oxidation with NaBiO_3 , adding an excess of Mohr's salt and back-titrating with KMnO_4 , or by oxidation with periodate and determining colorimetrically in a Lumetron colorimeter; Zn, by Lang's ferricyanide method; Co, colorimetrically by nitroso R-salt reagent; Ni, colorimetrically as nickelic dimethylglyoxime or gravimetrically as nickelous dimethylglyoxime; Cr, iodimetrically or colorimetrically with diphenylcarbazide solution acidified with phthalic anhydride using dichromate as comparison standard. The reagents used in the present investigation were of AnalaR grade. Some portion of the exchange studies described in this paper has been reported earlier by one of the authors⁶.

The base-exchange capacities and exchangeable base contents (m.e./g.) of different clay systems, humic acids, and humates are recorded in Table I. The variations of selectivity coefficients with changes of equilibrium concentrations are represented graphically in Figs. 1 to 4. In order to have an idea about the selectivity of ionic species like NH_4^+ , K^+ , Na^+ , H^+ , Mg^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , and Al^{3+} on different clay salts and humate systems investigated, their selectivity coefficients at equilibrium concentrations equal to the saturation capacities of the clays are shown in Table II, wherein are also included the selectivity coefficients of Cu^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Cr^{3+} on H-clay and humic acid. The order of elution of the bivalent trace element cations Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , and Cu^{2+} , when exchanged against NH_4^+ , K^+ , Na^+ , H^+ (acid), H^+ (resin), Mg^{2+} , Al^{3+} ions, is shown in Table III. The selectivity coefficients were determined also at two other equilibrium concentrations, namely, 0.5 m.e./g. or 1.0 m.e./g. A more or less similar trend in their values was found as shown in Table III,

TABLE I

System	Cu-clay	Mn-clay	Zn-clay	Ni-clay	Co-clay	Cr-clay	H-clay (A)	H-clay (A ₁)	Humic acid	Cu-humate	Mn-humate	Ni-humate
B.e.c. (m.e./g.)	0.63	0.59	0.44	0.68	0.68	0.48	0.78	0.83	6.12	4.03	3.61	3.62

TABLE II

Selectivity coeff. at the equilibrium conc. equal to the saturation capacities of the ion-exchange systems.

System.	Electrolyte.								
	NH_4^+ $\times 10^2$.	K^+ $\times 10^2$.	Na^+ $\times 10^2$.	H^+ (acid) $\times 10^2$.	H^+ (resin) $\times 10^2$.	Mg^{2+} $\times 10^2$.	Ba^{2+} $\times 10^2$.	Al^{3+} $\times 10^2$.	
Cu-clay	1.0	1.0	..	15.2	3.8	..	96	..	
Mn- "	2.3	..	0.4	21.5	21.5	137	..	..	
Zn- "	1.6	..	0.4	..	26.0	..	..	..	
Ni- "	2.6	2.0	1.7	8.5	4.5	104	..	4.05×10^5	
Co- "	2.5	2.1	1.8	6.7	5.7	116	..	14.7×10^5	
Cr- "	7.0×10^{-5}	2.1×10^{-5}	2.1×10^{-5}	...	..	2000×10^{-5}	..	96	
	$\text{Cu}^{2+} \times 10^2$.	$\text{Mn}^{2+} \times 10^2$.	$\text{Zn}^{2+} \times 10^2$.	$\text{Ni}^{2+} \times 10^2$.	$\text{Co}^{2+} \times 10^2$.	$\text{Cr}^{3+} \times 10^2$.			
H-clay	7.20	6.150	3.300	3.750	3.3	112			
Humic acid	18.05	0.415	0.445	0.575					
				$\text{H}^+ \times 10^2$.		$\text{Mg}^{2+} \times 10^2$.			
Cu-humate				300		0.78			
Mn- "				..		24.00			
Ni- "				730		0.50			

TABLE III

Ion.	Order of elution.
Al^{3+}	..
Mg^{2+}	..
H^+ (resin)	..
H^+ (acid)	..
Na^+	..
K^+	..
NH_4^+	..
	$\text{Co} > \text{Ni}$
	$\text{Mn} > \text{Co} > \text{Ni}$
	$\text{Zn} > \text{Mn} > \text{Co} > \text{Ni} > \text{Cu}$
	$\text{Mn} > \text{Cu} > \text{Co} > \text{Ni}$
	$\text{Co} > \text{Ni} > \text{Zn} = \text{Mn}$
	$\text{Co} > \text{Ni} > \text{Cu}$
	$\text{Ni} > \text{Co} > \text{Mn} > \text{Zn} > \text{Cu}$

DISCUSSION

The selectivity coefficient for particular ion pairs has been used to characterise synthetic ion exchangers. This characterisation is based on the fact that the selectivity coefficient remains fairly constant over a wide range of concentration⁸. The observed constancy of selectivity coefficients on synthetic exchangers suggests that the ideal condition of equality of their exchange spots may be more or less realised. Pochhali⁷, however, observed with some synthetic ion exchangers that the logarithmic plots of the ratios, and not the ratios themselves, of the concentrations of the ions in the resin phase against the logarithm of the ratios of the concentrations of the ions in the solution phase gave linear graphs with definite intercepts.

Evidence of the heterogeneous character of the clay surface has been obtained from crystal chemical⁹ as well as ion-exchange⁹ studies. This has been further corroborated by the results of calculation of selectivity coefficients of a number of ion pairs on montmorillonite and humic acid surfaces, represented graphically in Figs. 1 to 4.

FIG. 1

7. *This Journal*, 1960, 37, 451.

8. Marshall, "The Colloid Chemistry of the Silicate Minerals", 1949, Academic Press Inc., New York.

9. Mukherjee and Ganguly, *J. Phys. Coll. Chem.*, 1951, 55, 1420.

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

Selectivity coefficients have been plotted against the equilibrium concentration of the added cation. A constancy of the selectivity coefficient would give linear graphs. Instead, the graphs show, except in a few cases only, a wide variation of selectivity coefficients. The variations are generally more marked at the low concentration range. At the higher range of concentration the trend is towards approximately constant values. Selectivity coefficients, calculated from the data on H-clay and humic acid systems, show an increase at first, followed by a maximum, whereas the reverse is the case with the values calculated from the data on clay-salts and humates. Whenever in the latter systems the solution phase contains H^+ ions or a bivalent ion, e.g., Mg^{2+} , the selectivity coefficients show a sudden fall, followed either by a minimum or a tendency to attain constant values. With the monovalent cations, viz., Na^+ , K^+ , and NH_4^+ , in the solution phase the selectivity coefficients are constant within certain limits over the concentration range studied.

FIG. 4

In spite of the variations noted in the magnitude of selectivity coefficients, an approximate idea regarding the selectivity of different ionic species like NH_4^+ , K^+ , Na^+ , H^+ , Mg^{2+} , and Al^{3+} on the clay systems investigated can be obtained from Table II. The order of affinity of the above ionic species therefore seems to be approximately: $Al^{3+} > Mg^{2+} > H^+$ (acid) $> H^+$ (resin) $> NH_4^+ \gg K^+ > Na^+$.

Al^{3+} , Mg^{2+} , and Ba^{2+} ions have been included in the series because our experiments have been carried out in sufficiently dilute solutions. The greater selectivity of the proton of acid than that of the proton from H-resin is due to the facts that (i) pH is low in the former case and (ii) acid is in direct contact with the exchanger. Similarly, the order of selectivity, on

H-clay and humic acid, of the trace element cations Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , and Ni^{2+} follows respectively the series:

The order of elution of the trace element cations is expected to be the reverse of their order of adsorption. This is more or less verified in the case of Co^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , and Cu^{2+} , but not in the case of Mn^{2+} and Zn^{2+} ions, as shown in Table III. The order of elution of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , and Mn^{2+} ions from the corresponding humates, when exchanged against Mg^{2+} , follows as expected the series: $\text{Mn}^{2+} > \text{Ni}^{2+} > \text{Cu}^{2+}$.

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